

Biofractal Devices

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Abstract— Development of revolutionary biofractal and novel organic bio-inspired devices using non-integer methodology is the focus of this paper. Non-integer methodology is explored in the form of a quantitative biofractal architecture, which incorporates ontogenic and epigenetic scalable mechanisms for multiple signal carriers, fragility and dimensional scalability in the development of nonlinear sensor models and methodology. Biofractal devices will provide a precision, low power, low weight integrated real-time sensory capability for mobile platforms applications such as unmanned air vehicles, emerging optical communication, and radar.

I. INTRODUCTION

The overall field of molecular electronics is an interdisciplinary field involving the multiphysics effect of ionic and electronics in areas of multiple signal carriers and fragility at the interface between chemistry, electrical engineering, optical engineering, and nanoscience [1]. *Molecular electronics* is defined as the encoding, manipulation, and retrieval of information at a molecular or macromolecular level [2]. Molecular electronic devices (which includes both biological and nonbiological molecules as shown in Fig. 1) greatly miniaturizes computer circuitry and provides promising new methodologies for high-speed signal processing, communication, radar, volumetric data storage, novel associative memory and neural networks, and linear and nonlinear devices[3].

A biofractal device defines the unique subclass of molecular electronics characterized by multi-logic states in three dimensional organic protein structures [3]. These effects include the femtosecond dynamics of the excited states, energy transfer, reactions of the photochemical cycle, and the role and function of the novel retinal structural rotation characteristics [2]. Historically the early work on molecular electronics began from 1975 to 1995, when scientists in the former Soviet Union began to explore protein-based polymer films containing *bacteriorhodopsin* as a replacement for our modern day solid-state computers [4,5]. The protein-based polymer film structure revealed unusual energy switching features, and provided a unique background for understanding mechanisms of energy and proton transfer [5].

Figure 1. Molecular Electronic Devices (Ref DARPA)

II. QUANTITATIVE BIOFRACTAL ARCHITECTURE

Scientists using *bacteriorhodopsin* for biofractal devices exploit the fact that the protein (retinal) cycles through a series of spectrally distinct intermediates upon absorption of light. The protein *bacteriorhodopsin* (BR) has many properties that make it attractive for various applications. BR is stable, long-lived, and can be produced in large amounts. BR has long been considered for applications ranging from optical memory, holographic interferometers for nondestructive testing, chemical sensor and as the active element in a variety of microelectronic devices [3]. *Bacteriorhodopsin* converts light into a refractive index change with remarkable efficiency (approximately 65 percent) and the protein is 10 times smaller than the wavelength of light.

The idea of using protein as a metamaterial for a biofractal device is made possible by the fact that proteins exist in different conformations, or states, and that in certain proteins these states can be induced by light. This paper is focusing on exploring the modeling properties of components for this unique protein mechanism as a biofractal device. The realization that the use of fractional-order derivatives can lead to the quantitative formation of a 3-D quantitative biofractal architecture that could be modeled in a closed form solution [6] will be explored in Section III of this paper. These fractional-order expressions required only a parametric gain constant variation between rectangular and spherical coordinates which were more functional and less complex than Fick's laws of diffusion [7].

The difficult implementation aspects for noninteger fractals have been known for over a hundred years. Isaac Newton was said to get headaches thinking about the 3-body problem (Sun, Moon, and Earth). Actually, the biofractals are based on the structural variation of molecules similar to the 3-body problem, thus the reason for the 3-D modeling, and hence the complexity of the calculations. Unfortunately, the direct applications of numerical methods that work well in one or two dimensions often are not usable in three dimensions. Increasing the degrees of freedom related to 3-D mechanical modeling, requires non-integer fractional derivation, where it can correctly model the viscoelastically damped structures [8], similar to the physical phenomenon of biofractal devices involving protein structures. It is believed that the resulting fractional parameters of such non-integer order models should have a close link with the physical characteristics of the protein system. It has been shown [8], that the fractional parameters are precise, few in number and are valid to model a wide frequency range.

Figure 2. Time Response of the BR Chromophore's Rotational Mechanical Movement due to Absorption of Light

The BR photoelectric effect is shown in Fig. 2, the retinal structure (highlighted by the circle) rotates due to the energy absorption of light upon the BR chromophore that surrounds its' structure. As the retinal structure rotates a fast charge migration toward the positive shift base results in the B1 component, followed by slower B2, B3, and B4 signals, all within a one picosecond time span, in some cases. B3 results from ionic flux charge motion involving the proton pump, within the chromophore.

The absorbed photons are measured in Fig. 3. The photons that were not used in the chromophore's chemical reaction will be assumed to have been transduced to heat or scattered off, no longer to interfere with the material (although heat does have some effect on the photocycle, see [5]). The photons absorbed by the BR for either the primary or branched photocycles are transduced into mechanical energy

and assumed to be absorbed by the surrounding lipid membrane and diffused away. The total photons values for the branched photocycles (B1-B4 of Fig.2) are the input energy values for the fractional-order equation using a spring-mass analogous to the 3-D retinal movement within the protein chromophore as developed in the next section of this paper.

Figure 3. Shows Magnitude and Phase Response of the resolved absorption spectra of *Bacteriorhodopsin*. The phase angle on the right axis.

Figure 4. Forward and Backward Repeatability of the Chromophore's Response

In Fig. 4, the "forward" and "backward" indications notes whether the measurement was taken from 400nm to 750nm (forward), or from 750nm to 400nm (backward) showing that

the retinal response has a memory of the previous energy state.

In the model, the effect of this simultaneous energy diffusion onto adjacent protein is assumed to constrain the mechanical movement of the adjacent protein, thereby perhaps accounting for some of the retinal inefficiencies. The retinal energy barrier is 15kcal/mol, and the return state is an additional 45kcal/mol. In addition to this energy barrier, a diffused mechanical constraint from nearby BR photoisomerizations must be applied to the energy model as well. The model in the future, will calculate the energy barriers required for bit-changing for each protein. Also, this model runs on the assumption that macromolecular mechanical movements account for the most significant and quantitative aspects of protein energy interactions. Electrostatic and other quantum mechanical energies that may be involved are simply ignored for sake of simplicity.

III. FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES

Many fractional-order algorithms and processes are modeled using LC and RC circuits [6,7]. The fraction derivative is an effective means for handling nonlinear characteristics of actual systems such as electromagnetic theory, fluid flow and diffusion, and electrical networks. The fractional order derivative is a linear operator that arises in the some special applications as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Fractional-Order Algorithm Applications

Theory	Application
Diffusion Process	Multi-Logic
Modeling Measured Transfer Functions	Mechanical Damping and E& M Waves
Transcendental Transfer Functions	Unsteady Device Dynamics
Linear System State Formulations	New Forms of Control Theory
Physical Phenomena	Fractals and Chaos

A key feature of the fractional order derivatives is that it can capture the weak frequency dependence in a simple transfer function. The fractional order derivative is defined as

$$D_{(t)}^{\alpha}[u(t)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t \frac{u(t-\tau)}{\tau^{\alpha}} d\tau \quad 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (1)$$

The Laplace transform is defined as

$$L[U(t)] = U(s) \quad (2)$$

$$L[\dot{U}(t)] = sU(s) - U(0) \quad (3)$$

The Laplace transform of a fractional order derivative is defined as

$$L[D_{(t)}^{\alpha}U(t)] = s^{\alpha}U(s) \quad (4)$$

The Composition Property is shown in Equation 5.

$$D^{\alpha}D^{\beta}x(t) = D^{\alpha+\beta}x(t) \quad (5)$$

Consider Newton Second Law, in terms of mapping fractional order parameters to behavior. It was shown by Bagley's work [8], that once Newton's law is in one-half order fractional, shown in Equation 6, observed physical phenomena parameters can be directly mapped to the model.

$$\bar{F} = D_{(t)}^{1/2}(D_{(t)}^{1/2}\bar{p}) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 5 shows the biofractal model characteristics that are required to be mapped into the transfer function H(s). Without changing the nature of events (retinal states: Q,M,L,P,N,K,O) as shown in Fig. 5 the model viewpoint taken controls the effect of predictions for the given phenomenon (photoelectric states: B1,B2,B3, B4 in Fig.2). This simply means that one must adapt to the best system of measurement for the given application. Many times this adaptation involves the transition of the system description into a fractional-order model that is based on a spring-mass-visco damped dynamic system[9,10].

Figure 5. Biofractal Device Transfer Function Characteristics.

Figure 6. Spring-Mass-Visco Damped Dynamic System [9].

The equations describing Fig. 6, Spring-mass-visco damped dynamic system are [See Ref. 9, page 89-90].

$$F_1 = -K_2 D_1^{\alpha_1} (x_0 - x_{m1}) \quad (7)$$

$$F_1 = K_1 (x_{m1} - x_2) \quad (8)$$

$$F_2 = -K_3 D_1^{\alpha_2} (x_0 - x_{m2}) \quad (9)$$

$$F_2 = -K_4 D_1^{\alpha_3} (x_{m2} - x_1) \quad (10)$$

Where the above symbols are defined as, K: Damping coefficients, M: Mass, F: Force and X: Displacement. Solving Eqns. 7-10 using the Laplace transform and eliminating x_{m1} and x_{m2} results in:

$$F_1(s) = \left(\frac{-K_2 s^{\alpha_1}}{1 + \frac{K_2}{K_1} s^{\alpha_1}} \right) (x_0 - x_1) \quad (11)$$

$$F_2(s) = \left(\frac{-K_3 s^{\alpha_2}}{1 + \frac{K_3}{K_4} s^{\alpha_2 - \alpha_3}} \right) (x_0 - x_1) \quad (12)$$

Solving Eqn. 11 and Eqn. 12, for the transfer function H(s) in Fig. 5 becomes.

$$H(s) = \frac{x_0(s)}{x_1(s)} = \frac{\frac{1}{K_4} s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2} + \frac{1}{K_3} s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_3} + C}{\frac{m}{K_2 K_3} s^{2 + \alpha_3} + \frac{m}{K_1 K_3} s^{2 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_3} + D + E} \quad (13)$$

Where:

$$C = \frac{1}{K_2} s^{\alpha_2 + \alpha_3} + \frac{1}{K_1} s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3}$$

$$D = \frac{m}{K_1 K_4} s^{2 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2} + \frac{1}{K_4} s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2} + \frac{1}{K_3} s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_3}$$

$$E = \frac{1}{K_2} s^{\alpha_2 + \alpha_3} + \frac{1}{K_1} s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3}$$

Reduction of Eqn. 13, for α_3 , where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 = 0$, yields Eqn. 14

$$H(s) = \frac{x_0(s)}{x_1(s)} = \frac{\frac{K_4}{m} s^{\alpha_3} + \frac{K_1}{m}}{s^2 + \frac{K_4}{m} s^{\alpha_3} + \frac{K_1}{m}} \quad (14)$$

The frequency response of H(s) in Figure 7, shows that $\alpha_3 = 0.25$ begins to fit some of the key performance signatures of Fig. 4, without a normalized frequency[9].

Figure 7. Bode Plot of Mass-Spring-Viscoelastic Damper Transfer Function H(s) varying α_3 from 0 to 2 by steps of 0.2[9].

IV. SUMMARY

This paper addresses the unique methodology of incorporating fractional-order spring-mass-visco damped transfer function models to characterize the dynamics of the biofractal device. The idea in exploring the multidimensional characteristics of biofractal devices involves multilevel *state* interaction, where the system has 3-D structural deformations in the form of retinal conformations. These biofractal protein devices can be converted into linearized fractional-order derivative models for weak frequency dependency and time response protein model characterization. Current biofractal models are now faced with high frequency design, due to the emergence of bio-nanodevices. The protein 3-D model and its *correct* development is probably the most difficult aspect for biofractal device characterization. It is envisioned that biofractal devices will be integrated into chemical sensors, fluidic computer systems, optical switches, nanoactuators, self-repairing polymorphic computing systems, cognitive processors and biorobotics, whereby providing real-time sensory capability for mobile platforms such as unmanned air vehicles, multi-mode optical communication, and distributed radar systems.

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